

CoARA WG TIER – References for Communication and Training on gender bias

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Introduction

This document presents references for Communication and training on gender bias suggested by TIER members. It includes information about existing videos and tools to cope with bias in research assessment. A brief description, the link, and an image are provided for each reference.

Analyzed videos

<p>UCLA: 7 videos on implicit bias equity.ucla.edu/know/implicit-bias/</p>	<p>Videos</p> <p> Implicit Bias Preface: Biases and...</p>
<p>Interaction and group dynamics in evaluation Committees by NOW www.youtube.com/watch?v=zvRbd40KPyo</p>	<p>The video provided by NOW, the Dutch Research Council, regards Biased Language, Criteria, Structure, Time and Accountability. When the assessment committee convenes, the interaction with the applicants and the group dynamic are very important. Therein may lie challenges leading to a suboptimal assessment. These challenges can play a role during presentations and interviews with applicants, or during the committee meeting in which the assessment of the applications takes place.</p>

The background noise Il rumore di fondo by Italian National Research Council CNR (2023)

The video was produced for sensitize the evaluation committees on bias in evaluation, including but not limited to gender bias. Checked by Laura and Lucio.

<https://tube.rsi.cnr.it/w/4a1yoWa9QsjHQtrhbrAMB>

Recruitment Bias in Research Institutes by Cerca - Research Centers of Catalonia (2016)

The European gender portal <https://www.genderportal.eu/resources/recruitment-bias-research-institutes> links this video.

The video aims to train male and female evaluators on assessment panels about recruitment bias. This bias - often subconscious - is particularly detrimental to women, leading them to perceive assessment as hostile.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g978T58gELo>

Videos to fulfil gender awareness approach by Swiss National Science Foundation SNSF (2024) SPIRIT (snf.ch)

Target: Applicants for research funding. Consider sex and gender in the research topic; Consider gender in the team composition

<https://www.snf.ch/en/nlghrhyzbD90TM9D/funding/programmes/spirit>

Bias in peer review training module by Canadian Institutes of Health Research CIHR, NSERC and SSHRC (2022)

Interactive training module for evaluation committees.

It considers gender and other biases such as age, Institutional affiliation, career stage, anti-Indigenous, and language biases.

cihr-irsc.gc.ca/lms/e/bias/

Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators' by FNR- Luxembourg National Research Fund & DORA (2021)

A video for responsible research assessment.

It provides a 'checklist' of six concrete suggestions for research funders seeking to improve responsible assessment of funding applications.

<https://sfdora.org/resource/balanced-broad-responsible-a-practical-guide-for-research-evaluators>

Understanding unconscious bias (2015)

<https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/publications/2015/unconscious-bias/>

Useful tools and references

Gvozdanović, J., & Maes, K. (2018). Implicit bias in academia: A challenge to the meritocratic principle and to women's careers – And what to do about it. LERU, N.23.

www.leru.org/files/implicit-bias-in-academia-full-paper.pdf

UCLA Equity, Diversity and Inclusion. (2019). Searching for Excellence. Evidence-Based Strategies for Equitable and Inclusive Faculty Hiring (p. 41). University of California, Los Angeles.

<https://ucla.app.box.com/v/searching-for-excellence>

	<p>NWO – Dutch Research Council: Webpage with practical advice on how to limit <i>implicit bias</i> in recruitment www.nwo.nl/en/assessment-committee-meetings</p> <p>NOW Factsheet. The factsheet can be used to help implementing the suggestions given in the video ‘interaction and group dynamics in evaluation committees’ https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/mediafiles/NWO-handout-inclusive-assessment-tools-for-evaluation-committee-meetings.pdf</p>
<p>SEE BIAS / BLOCK BIAS™</p> <p>A METHODOLOGY TO DIAGNOSE BIAS VMware Women's Leadership Innovation Lab Stanford University</p>	<p>Stanford toolbox</p> <p>This tool provides an evidence-based approach to diagnose bias. Diagnosing bias will enable change agents to more effectively design solutions and convince others in the organization that bias does exist in the culture. Diagnosing bias plays essential roles in improving diversity and inclusion program efficacy.</p> <p>https://womensleadership.stanford.edu/resources/tools</p>
<p>Higher Education Quarterly</p> <p>RESEARCH ARTICLE </p> <p>Reconsidering the Assessment Criteria in Academic Recruitment</p> <p>Maria Pietilä¹ Jonni Kekäle² Katri Rintamäki²</p> <p><small>¹University of Eastern Finland, Suonenranta, Finland ²University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland</small></p>	<p>M.Pietilä, J.Kekäle, K. Rintamäki (2025). Reconsidering the Assessment Criteria in Academic Recruitment. Higher Education Quarterly, 2025; 79:e70068.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.70068</p>

<p>Chemistry A European Journal</p> <p>Employment Survey for European Chemists (ESEC3) How Diverse is Europe's Chemical Workforce?</p> <p>Prof. Dr. Reiner Salzer, Dr. Nineta Hrastelj, Prof. Dr. Anthony Smith</p> <p>First published: 16 May 2024 https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.202401222</p>	<p>Reiner Salzer, Nineta Hrastelj, and Anthony Smith (2024). Employment Survey for European Chemists (ESEC3). How Diverse is Europe's Chemical Workforce? Chem. Eur. J. 2024, 30, e202401222 doi.org/10.1002/chem.202401222</p> <p>https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/chem.202401222</p>
<p>eua EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY ASSOCIATION</p> <p>Reforming Academic Career Assessment: current insights and future directions</p> <p>25 June 2024</p>	<p>European University Association EUA online workshop 25 June 2024 Reforming Academic Career Assessment current insights and future directions. Recordings and slides available.</p> <p>https://eua.eu/events/327-reforming-academic-career-assessment-current-insights-and-future-directions.html</p>
<p>Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool</p> <p>Making universities and research organisations equal for women and men</p> <p>The Gender Equality in Academia and Research (GEAR) tool provides universities</p>	<p>GEAR toolkit: Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool by European Institute for Gender Equality - EIGE</p> <p>https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear?language_content_entity=en</p>

GEECCO
Gender Equality in Engineering through
Communication and Commitment

WP 7
D7.2. Promoting gender equality in the
evaluation process: Guideline for jury
members, reviewers and research funding
organizations' employees

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GEECCO. "Deliverable 7.2: Promoting Gender Equality in the Evaluation Process: Guidelines for Jury Members, Reviewers and Research Funding Organizations' Employees", April 2020.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5ce76bdf5&appId=PPGMS>

Webinar - How can RFOs fight gender bias
18 November 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 741112.

Webinar #2. How can RFOs fight gender bias, SUPERA project (2020)

In this webinar, two RFOs who have invested in the understanding of the phenomenon and started to take actions will share their experiences: ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche) and TA CR (the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic).

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HJ65dMBAcAU>

A closer look at unconscious bias and what RFOs can do

Webinar #04: A closer look to unconscious bias and what RFOs can do

Webinar #04: A closer look to unconscious bias and what RFOs can do, SUPERA project (2021).

This is the 4th webinar organised by SUPERA and specifically dedicated to gender equality in research funding organisations.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G0q-gcWhZZI>

<p>The screenshot shows the Reformscape website interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Reformscape', 'The Declaration', 'Project TARA', 'DORA Reports', and 'News and Resources'. A search bar contains the text 'bias'. Below the search bar, there are several search results listed, including 'Searching for Excellence & Diversity: Increasing the Hiring of Women Faculty at One Academic Medical Center', 'Practices that can Minimize the Impact of Implicit Bias in Attracting and Evaluating Candidates', and 'Recruiting for Excellence'.</p>	<p>Resources from DORA's Reformscape platform on biases</p> <p>https://sfdora.org/reformscape/source-materials/?_tara_keyword_search=bias</p>
<p>The screenshot shows the 'Recognising and rewarding open research' toolkit page. The main heading is 'A toolkit for recognising and rewarding open research'. The text describes the toolkit as a resource for higher education institutions to improve their research assessment practices. It mentions that the toolkit was developed by the UK Higher Education Sector and is part of the UK Higher Education Sector's research assessment reform project.</p>	<p>Toolkit for recognising and rewarding open research (OR4 2021–2027) by UK Reproducibility Network.</p> <p>https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/</p>
<p>The screenshot shows the DORA introductory course page. The main heading is 'The DORA introductory course on responsible research assessment'. The text describes the course as a self-paced, free resource designed to help researchers challenge existing assumptions around research quality and impact. It mentions that the course is available in multiple languages and is designed to be flexible and self-paced.</p>	<p>Introductory Course on Responsible Research Assessment. by DORA</p> <p>https://sfdora.org/courses/introductory-course-to-responsible-research-assessment/</p>
<p>The image shows the cover of the 'UNCONSCIOUS BIAS' video catalog. It features a stylized illustration of five diverse people in a meeting setting. The title 'UNCONSCIOUS BIAS' is prominently displayed in large, bold, white letters on a dark purple background.</p>	<p>CoARA EXPECT Video Catalog (2025)</p> <p>19 videos addressing various aspects of research assessment, produced by EXPECT CoARA Boost Project</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/17648971</p>

MOOC by University of Padova (2026) - Gender Dimension in Research: Concepts, Practices and Impact

Massive Open Online Course with the module “Beyond Metrics: Valuing People, Teams, and Societal Impact in Research. Introducing the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment” introducing CoARA and CoARA WG TIER

<https://lifelonglearning.unipd.it/local/dashboard/addon/dashboard/dashboard.php?id=82>